

NOTES

Derivatographic Study of Bis-(salicylate)diaquozinc(II)

H. C. MISHRA, R. R. JHA

Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University, 834 008

and

S. N. MUKHERJEE

Mineral Technology Div., C. F. R. I., Dhanbad, India

Manuscript received 25 January 1979, accepted 23 February 1979

A number of workers¹⁻⁴ have prepared and characterised the zinc salicylate by different methods but derivatographic study of bis(salicylate)diaquozinc(II) complex has not been reported. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of bis(salicylate)diaquozinc(II) by derivatographic method (D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. method).

Experimental

The complex has been prepared by dissolving zinc carbonate in hot aqueous solution of salicylic acid in stoichiometric proportion 1 : 2 metal ligand ratio. The crystal was obtained by slow evaporation of the solution at room temperature. The product is collected on a filter, washed with cold water and ethanol and dried in air. The analysis of the complex was carried out by usual chemical methods. Zinc was determined by E.D.T.A. method⁵. The carbon and hydrogen by element estimation technique (Found Zn-17.64%, C-44.74%, H-3.7% calculated for $[\text{Zn}(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ Zn-17.44%, C-44.8%, and H-4.12%). The complex is almost insoluble in cold water but dissolves appreciably in hot water. The aqueous solution of bis(salicylate)diaquozinc(II) produces violet coloration with ferric chloride solution. This indicates that phenolic -OH is either free or weakly bonded with Zn(II) ion. The complex is diamagnetic and does not exhibit electronic absorption band in the region 350-1000 nm. The complex is stable up to 80° and gradually loses water molecule and becomes anhydrous at 140°.

Derivatographic Study :

The derivatography of the system of Paulik, Paulik and Erdey manufactured by M/s M.O.M. (Hungary Optical Works) have been employed for the present study. The instrument record the different functions photographically like D.T.G.,

D.T.A., T.G.A. and temperature T. For D.T.A. ignited alumina has been used as an inert material and ceramic sample holder for both inert and test material. For combined D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. study of a sample of 600 mg bis(salicylate)diaquozinc(II) was carried out with heating rate of 8°/min in static air. The temperature was fixed between 30° to 800°.

Here the dehydration occurs in one step as indicated by one endotherm. The dehydration starts at 85° and ends at 140°. The peak on D.T.A. curve shows that the reaction starts at 80° and ends at 180°. The inflexion point of the endotherm is at 120°. The loss in weight in this range is of 56 mg (required loss for 2H₂O molecule is 57.6 mg). The loss in weight in T.G.A. curve indicates that all the two water molecules associated with $[\text{Zn}(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ are of similar nature.

The second step starts at 155° and ends at 220° as shown by D.T.G. curve. This is shown by a small endothermal peak in D.T.A. curve. The loss in this region is of 20 mg as shown by T.G.A. curve. The product is not identified at this step. The D.T.G. curve indicates that the third step starts at 220° and ends at 290°. This is shown by an endothermal peak in D.T.A. curve. The endothermal curve starts at 225° and continues till 320°. The inflexion point of the endothermal peak is at 265°. The loss in this region is of 210 mg as indicated by T. G. A. curve, indicating that the elimination of a salicylic acid molecule has taken place. The product obtained at this step, almost corresponds with the required weight of $[\text{Zn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})]$.

The decomposition of the complex starts at 360° and ends at 500° as indicated by D.T.G. curve. In this region two types of reaction takes place : first is exothermic and other is endothermic. The inflexion point of the exothermic peak is at 440° and that of endothermal peak is at 470°. The loss in weight in T.G. curve indicates that the product obtained at this step corresponds with the weight of basic ZnO - ZnCO₃.

The last step of decomposition starts at 500° and ends at 650°. This is shown by a broad exothermal peak in D.T.A. curve. The loss in weight in this range is of 35mg (i.e., total loss in weight is 470 mg). Product obtained at this stage corresponds with the required weight for ZnO, which is further confirmed quantitatively.

